

ID-1244

3D COMPUTER SIMULATIONS OF RESIN MOLDING

Piotr Saj

ABB Corporate Research, Kraków, Poland

SUMMARY: The selected results of 3D computer simulation of reactive molding process for manufacturing of voltage transformers are presented. The simulation has been based on FLUENT computer code. Due to complexity of the process, curing kinetics and viscosity models were implemented in calculations. Analysis of process, including filling and post-filling is included. Based on the simulation a set of process problems can be found out. Obtained results allow us to optimise process parameters and produce components with better durability and quality.

KEYWORDS: curing, RTM, 3D simulation, mould filling, reactive moulding

INTRODUCTION

The production processes involving mould filling and curing of thermosetting materials have increasing share in manufacturing of specialised industrial equipment. Various fabrication methods are used depending on the material and on the product. Through the design of the process parameters one has good control over the mechanical and electrical properties of the components, making these processes very attractive for Medium Voltage / High Voltage apparatus in high volume production. Therefore it becomes important to have a good knowledge of the phenomena taking place during the processes.

Computer simulations help to reduce costs of new components development by decreasing number of necessary moulding trials. In addition, design and production times are reduced enabling for faster implementation of the product onto the market. Complexity of the phenomena, different processes taking place at the same time, and finally, the necessity to calculate multi-disciplinary problem allowed only 2D simulations to be successfully performed so far. Recently so called 2.5-dimensional modelling [1],[4] has been applied, but such simulations can handle only with thin-walled elements. Taking this into account, it is obvious that implementation of the simulations based on 3D models is a very interesting subject from scientific as well as technical point of view. However, to realise it, it is necessary to develop new simulations approach and use powerful computers which allow us for fast calculations with high accuracy.

Simulation of injection moulding process of thermosetting materials is one of the areas where advanced hardware and software must be used. Such computer simulations provide useful information to detect moulding problems prior to mould making, such as premature gelation, undesired weld-line locations and air traps [4],[7]. The computer simulations based on FEM and FVM (finite elements and finite volumes methods) help mould designers to determine gate locations, part size and they support process engineers in identifying optimum process conditions (filling time, inlet temperature, mould wall temperature).

The paper presents selected results of 3D simulations of reactive moulding process used in manufacturing of voltage transformers.

TECHNOLOGY

RTM – Resin Transfer Moulding is very widely used method to manufacture thin structures called composites which include a reinforcement. A type of RTM is Reactive Moulding - a manufacturing of components without any reinforcement. Additionally, the

components are characterised by relatively bulk frame. Generally, the method may be delineated into a set of stages, which are presented in **Fig. 1**.

The first step, *preparing* consists in assembling and pre-heating of internal parts of the product (core, coils, etc.), placing them in the mould and in parallel, mixing the resin system. The final resin mixture should be stored in proper temperature conditions. Keeping of the resin system for a long time in too high temperature can cause premature gelation, so the material can not be used any more.

The second stage, *filling* begins when the hot mould is closed and resin mixture is injected into the mould cavity. The fluid flows around and through the internal parts until the mould is fulfilled. Heat transfer during this phase predominantly results in conduction from the mould walls to the fluid so that the flow is non-isothermal. The polymerisation process starts during this step, thus the total time of filling should not be too long. In the opposite case too early cured resin can block the flow and the cavity will not be filled completely.

Fig. 1 Scheme of Reactive Moulding technology

Once the filling is finished, the phase of *post-filling* starts. This step is the most important from the final quality point of view. The curing phenomena should proceed in proper order. The ideal situation is when gelling process starts from the point, which is located at the longest distance from injection slot, and ends close to the inlet region. The highly exothermic chemical reaction accompanies the curing process, so it affects significantly the heat transfer. A chemical shrinkage of the cured material which results in decreasing of casting volume is an additional phenomenon occurring in this stage. Thus preventive action should be applied to avoid micro-porosities forming. The overpressure of feeding material is the most often used method.

The final stage, *secondary heat treatment*, takes place after the curing reaction is complete. The component is de-moulded and undergoes secondary heat treatment, usually in tunnel furnace. The main goal of this operation is to release of mechanical stresses.

BASIC EQUATIONS

CFD (Computer Fluid Dynamics) computations involve the solution of a large number of coupled non-linear equations. These equations can be difficult to solve, unless the solution is matched to the problem physics. The equations representing the conservation of mass, momentum and energy in Cartesian coordinates system ($x_j, j=1, 2, 3$) have the following forms:

a) mass conservation equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\rho u_i)}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (1)$$

b) momentum conservation equation:

$$\frac{\partial (\rho u_j)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\rho u_i u_j)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_j} + \rho g_j + F_j \quad (2)$$

where:

τ_{ij} - stress tensor:

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) - \frac{2}{3} \mu \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} \delta_{ij} \quad (3)$$

ρ - fluid density, [kg/m³]

t - time, [s]

u_i - velocity, [m/s]

μ - molecular fluid viscosity coefficient, [kg/ms]

p - static pressure, [Pa]

g_j - gravity, [m/s²]

F_j - external body forces, [kg/m²s²]

$i, j = 1, 2, 3$.

c) energy equation:

$$\frac{\partial (\rho h)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\rho u_i h)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\mathbf{l} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \sum_j h_j G_{ji} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} - \tau_{ik} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_k} + h_s \quad (4)$$

where:

h_j - enthalpy of species j , [J/kg]

\mathbf{l} - thermal conductivity, [W/mK]

G_{ji} - flux of species j in the i -th, direction, [kg/s]

h_s - source term, [J/kg]

T - temperature, [K].

RHEOKINETIKS OF THERMOSETTING MATERIALS CURING

The reactive nature and complex rheology of reactive materials require appropriate characterisation of the viscosity and curing kinetics. Properties of material undergoing the curing process depend on its degree of curing α . Therefore it is necessary to use model, which must be based on the fact that viscosity of the material depends not only on temperature, but also on degree of curing. This relation is described by Macosko [2]:

$$\mathbf{h} = B \exp\left(\frac{T_b}{T}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{a}_g}{\mathbf{a}_g - \mathbf{a}}\right)^{C_1 + C_2 \mathbf{a}} \quad (5)$$

where:

- B, C_1, C_2, T_b - constants,
- T - the absolute temperature.
- $\mathbf{a}_g = 0.65$ (65% of cured material),
- \mathbf{a} - degree of curing, [%]

The rheokinetics parameters B, C_1, C_2 and T_b are obtained by measuring the cure behaviour using a dynamic mechanical spectrometer (DMS).

To determine kinetics of the curing process, Kamal's model is used very often [3]. According to this model a degree of curing at time t is defined as:

$$\mathbf{a} = \frac{H(t)}{H_\Sigma} \quad (6)$$

where:

- $H(t)$ - heat of reaction released at time t,
- H_S - total heat of reaction.

The equation showing curing rate is the following:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{a}}{dt} = (k_1 + k_2 \mathbf{a}^m) \cdot (1 - \mathbf{a})^n \quad (7)$$

$$k_i = A_i e^{\frac{-E_i}{RT}} \quad (8)$$

where:

- $i = 1, 2;$
- A_i - pre-exponential factors,
- m, n - constants,
- E_i - activation energies,
- k_i - reaction rate constants,
- R - the universal gas constant,

Heat of the reaction is used in energy equation as a source term (internal heat source).

INPUT DATA AND COMPUTATIONAL TIME

FLUENT (ver.5.4) software of Fluent Incorporated was applied to perform a computer simulation of filling and curing process of epoxy resin type CY225 [6].The theoretical models presented above, which describe viscosity changes and reaction kinetics of thermosetting materials were implemented in the Fluent software as user-defined-subroutines.

3D geometry and mesh

Geometry of the model studied is presented in **Fig. 2**. Using Gambit (Fluent's mesh generator) a mesh of finite volumes was created (**Fig. 3**). Due to complexity of the phenomena, size and number (about 80,000) of finite volumes was optimised to obtain relatively short time of calculations. This helped us to reduce a computational time to 2-3 days, depending on simulation parameters. Parallel calculations were carried out using Silicon Graphics Server ORIGIN 2000 with 2048MB of RAM, 2 processors R10000, 250MHz.

Fig. 2 Voltage transformer geometry
(cut – internal parts visible)

Fig. 3 Finite volume mesh
(external layout)

Boundary and initial conditions

As the geometric model had been created, all boundary and initial parameters were defined, which were necessary for simulation of moulding and curing process. The following parameters were included:

- pressure and initial temperature of in-flowing resin,
- mould walls temperature,
- resin and air material data,
- material data of core and windings.

The mould was modelled using constant temperature boundary condition on external casting walls. It allowed us to reduce the total number of finite volumes by approx. 30 per cent. As a result the calculation time was adequately shorter.

Computational time

Parallel processing on supercomputers, multiprocessor computers, or clusters of workstations enable for much faster calculations of complicated problems. Fluent offers options allowing to perform parallel calculations, therefore this possibility was used very often during these simulations. A number of tests were performed to determine differences in calculation time using different hardware configurations. **Table 1** presents selected data concerning calculation time of small part of the simulation.

For this comparison ORIGIN 2000 with one R10000 processor was used as the reference computer (acceleration factor 1.0).

Table 1. Comparison of calculation time for different hardware configurations

Calculation option	OCTANE 1xR10000 175MHz 768MB RAM	OCTANE 2xR10000 175MHz 768MB RAM	OCTANE 1xR12000 300MHz 512MB RAM	ORIGIN 2000 1xR10000 250MHz 2048MB RAM	ORIGIN 2000 2xR10000 250MHz 2048MB RAM
Calculation Time, s	2041	1170	1156	1256	610
Acceleration factor	0.62	1.07	1.09	1.0	2.06

SIMULATION RESULTS

Curing, which undergoes mainly during post-filling stage, is the most important fact of the process from the quality point of view. However to obtain exact temperature distribution field at the beginning of post-filling, it is necessary to simulate also the filling process, which involves many phenomena in the area of fluid dynamics, heat transfer, chemical reaction. This is the most time consuming stage of calculations requiring the use of advanced computer tools. **Fig. 4** and **Fig. 5** show resin phase (red colour) in different times of the filling stage.

Fig. 4 Filling after 10 seconds

Fig. 5 Filling after 119 seconds

From the results it can be noticed, that during filling stage, due to influx of cold material, and during early stage of the process the degree of curing at the central parts of the mould is lower than that near the mould wall. However, the curing reaction at the places where there is a bulk of resin accelerates during the process and overtakes the regions close to the mould wall. The inversion of temperature gradient over the cycle indicates that resin absorbs heat from the mould during the early stage and releases heat to the mould when curing process dominates.

In some simulation approaches researches neglected the filling stage due to complexity of flow calculation. They assumed the uniform, constant temperature distribution after filling equal to inlet temperature. In simulations presented here such assumption leads to incorrect results because the total time of filling is relatively long (4 minutes). The inflowing liquid is heated very intensively, and its temperature at the end of filling depends on its residence time in the hot mould. This is very clearly shown in **Fig. 6**.

Fig. 6 Temperature distribution at the end of filling stage (main cross-plane)

The polymerisation process is mainly controlled by temperature distribution. Therefore, starting of curing reaction in “left-upper” corner of the cavity is the natural consequence of presented above temperature field (**Fig. 7**). The picture is made using special technique called “iso-clip”: whole cavity is fulfilled by resin mixture, but only material having specified feature (here: the degree of curing above 65%) is visible. The 65% is a conventional threshold of solidification. Above this value the material can be found as solid. The degree of curing after 361 seconds of process is presented in **Fig. 8**.

Fig. 7 Degree of curing - end of filling – 240 sec.(iso-clip: 65-100%)

Fig. 8 Degree of curing after 361 sec. (iso-clip: 65-100%)

It was mentioned earlier that curing should proceed from the point, which is located at the longest distance from injection slot, and should finish close to the inlet region. This scenario allows us to feed the casting by fresh mixture until the post-filling stage is finished. The shrinkage undergoing during process is then compensated.

The results of the simulation demonstrated a wrong phenomenon of too early cured region close to feeding slot (**Fig. 9**). Presented below picture shows the region where the resin mixture cures as last. This is not “inlet region”. This is possible source of casting defects – some voids and micro-porosities can be formed at the pointed region.

Fig. 9 Degree of curing after 591 sec. (iso-clip: 0-65%)

One of very useful information received from simulations are time-history results. The temperature curves at three selected points are presented in **Fig. 10**. As it may be seen there are the temperature peaks being the result of highly exothermic curing reaction.

Fig. 10 Temperature in time curves in three selected points

CONCLUSIONS

The obtained results confirm feasibility of computer tools application for 3D simulations of complex processes like reactive moulding, where a set of many equations describing various phenomena have to be solved. Possibility of calculation of curing propagation in thermosetting materials has a very important meaning from the technical point of view, enabling to manufacture components with better quality and shorter production cycle. On the other hand, because of the complexity of the process appropriate hardware tools must be available if one needs fast and accurate calculations.

Based on the simulation results a set of process problems can be found out:

- improper filling (air traps),
- too fast curing (local overheating),
- high temperature gradients (crack source),
- wrong curing propagation.

The information allows us to formulate recommendations concerning process parameters: filling time, mould temperature, inlet temperature, etc. Consequently design and production times are reduced allowing for faster implementation of the product onto the market.

Parallel calculations decrease calculation time considerably (in some cases even more than twice), and simulations should be done using this option of calculations.

REFERENCES

- [1] V.W.Wang, L.S.Turng: *Simulation of Injection Mold Filling and Curing with Reactive Materials*, SPE Technical Papers, vol. 37, 1991.
- [2] C.W.Macosko: *RIM Fundamentals of Reaction Injection Molding*, Hanser, New York, 1989.
- [3] M.R.Kamal, S.Sourour and M.Ryan: *SPE Tech. Papers*, 19,S 187 (1973)
- [4] J.Grindling, M.Gehrig: *Introduction to FEM Based Computer Simulation to Assist molding and casting processes*, CIBA Speciality Chemicals Inc, Basel, 1998.
- [5] *FLUENT User's Guide*, Fluent Incorporated, Lebanon, 1998.
- [6] CIBA (Vantico), private communication.
- [7] Saj P. et. al., *Komputerowe symulacje wtrysku i utwardzania żywic epoksydowych w procesie wytwarzania przewodników prądowo-napięciowych IX Seminarium "Tworzywa sztuczne w budowie maszyn"*, Kraków, 2000 (in Polish)